

JCMST

NOVI SAD

2023

Supported by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science, Technological development and Innovation of the republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT BOOK

11 – 13 October 2023

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

Novi Sad, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

61(048.3)

THE PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology (2 ; 2023 ; Novi Sad)

Abstract book [Elektronski izvor] / The 2nd PSU-UNS Joint Conference on Medical Science and Technology 2023, 11-13 October 2023, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor-in-chief Rajko Jović]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Medicine, 2023. - 1 USB fleš memorija

Tiraž 150.

ISBN 978-86-7197-742-5

а) Медицинске науке -- Нове технологије -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 126492937

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Advisory Committee

Dejan Madić, Full Prof., Rector of the University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub, President, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., Dean of the Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Serbia

Assoc. Prof. Roengsak Leetanaporn, MD Dean of the Faculty of Medicine, PSU,
Thailand

Zoran Gojković, Assoc. Prof., Provincial Secretary for Healthcare

Zoran Milošević, Full Prof., Provincial Secretary for Higher Education and Scientific
Research

Scientific Committee

President Duško Kozić, Prof. Dr., Vice Dean for Research, MFNS, Serbia

Co-President Assoc. Prof. Teerha Piratvisuth, MD Vice Dean for
International Affairs

Scientific Committee Members

Snežana Brkić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Branislav Bajkin, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Zoran Komazec, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Srdić-Galić, Full Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Biljana Vučković, Assoc. Prof., MFNS, Serbia

Dragan Kravarušić, Full Prof., University of Tel Aviv "Sackler" Faculty of Medicine, Israel

Ludovico Abenavoli, Full Prof., University Magna Graecia of Catanzaro, Italy

Prof. Tippawan Liabsuetrakul, M.D., Ph.D. / Vice Dean for Research, Faculty of
Medicine, PSU

Joint Conference on
Medical Science and
Technology
NOVI SAD
2023

Prof. Surasak Sangkhathat, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Research, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Pasuree Sangsupawanich, M.D., Ph.D. / Assistant Dean for Hospital Affairs, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Prof. Boonsin Tangtrakulwanich, M.D. / Head of the Department of Orthopedics, Faculty of Medicine, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Srisurang Suttapreyasri / Associate Dean for Research and Graduate Studies, Faculty of Dentistry, PSU

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Karnsunaphat Balthip / Associate Dean for Research, Social Alliance, and International Affairs, Faculty of Nursing, PSU

Local Organizational Committee

Goran Stojiljković, Full Prof.

Mirela Erić, Full Prof.

Otto Barak, Full Prof.

Milica Jeremić-Knežević, Assoc. Prof.

Jasmina Boban, Assist. Prof.

Vedrana Karan Rakić, Assist. Prof.

Dubravka Klajić

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

Position 34

ANITICANCER MECHANISMS OF REPURPOSED DRUGS IN ONCOLOGY ON HAMSTER MODEL

Kosta J. Popović¹, Dušica J. Popović², Dejan Miljković³, Dušan Lalošević⁴,
Zana Dolićanin⁵, Ivan Čapo⁶ and Jovan K. Popović^{7*}

¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
kosta.popovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

²State University of Novi Pazar, Novi Pazar, Republic of Serbia
ducicapopovic@np.ac.rs

³Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
dejan.miljkovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁴Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
dusan.lalosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁵State University of Novi Pazar, Novi Pazar, Republic of Serbia
zdolicanin@np.ac.rs

⁶Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
ivan.capo@mf.uns.ac.rs

^{7*}Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
Corresponding author: **jovapopmf@gmail.com; jovan.popovic@mf.uns.ac.rs*

Introduction: Transcription factor NF-kB acts as an important target in oncology, as most of the molecules formed by transcription of genes trigger cancers. Also, ROS (Reactive Oxygen Species) activity is interconnected with NF-kB and cancer development. To identify NF-kB inhibition and/or ROS stimulation as antitumor mechanisms, we have screened combinations of currently approved non-oncological repurposed drugs that can inhibit hamster fibrosarcoma growth by rescuing cancer development with NF-kB stimulation and/or ROS inhibition.

Materials and methods: Male Syrian golden hamsters, weighing approximately 80 g, were randomly allocated to control and experimental groups (6 animals/group). 2×10^6 BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously into the animals' backs. Peroral treatments were carried out with metformin, caffeine, deoxycholic acid, 2-Deoxy-D-glucose, itraconazole, disulfiram and their selected combinations, via a gastric probe daily after cancer cell inoculation. Used drug with known NF-kB stimulatory effect was mebendazole. Used drug with known ROS inhibitory effect was nitroglycerin. In the course of experiment, tumor volumes were calculated using 3 diameters. After animal sacrifice, tumors were excised and their size, biophysical characteristics, histology and immunohistochemistry were assessed. Blood samples were collected for hematological and biochemical analyses and the main organs were toxicologically analyzed. Statistical significance was determined by one-way ANOVA followed by the Student-Newman-Keuls post hoc test.

Results: Two-drug combinations: metformin with caffeine, metformin with deoxycholic acid, metformin with 2-Deoxy-D-glucose, metformin with itraconazole and metformin with disulfiram can significantly ($P < 0.05$) suppress fibrosarcoma development in hamsters, given in doses equivalent to oncological human doses, without toxicity and influence on biochemical and hematological tests. Addition of NF-kB stimulator mebendazole or ROS inhibitor nitroglycerin to effective two-drug combinations containing metformin rescued cancer growth, indicating that these pathways may be responsible for antitumor action.

Figure: Tumor volume growth during course of the experiment: column chart with separated SEM values and interpolated lines between average values for groups that showed maximum and minimum response to therapy.

Conclusions: Among efficacious two-drug combinations, NF-kB inhibition and ROS activation were identified as anticancer mechanisms of action by rescue experiments with NF-kB activators and ROS inhibitors.

All efficacious combinations containing two repurposed drugs, that were recorded in our study on hamster fibrosarcoma, may be recommended for further clinical investigations.

Keywords: fibrosarcoma, hamsters, repurposed drugs, NF-kB, ROS

Acknowledgements:

This study was supported by the Republic of Serbia, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Provincial Secretariat for High Education and Scientific Research, grants nos. 142-451-3155/2022-02 (JM), 142-451-2626/2021 (DL) and Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, grant no. 451-03-68/2022-14/200114.